

TEACHING ENGLISH DENTAL FRICATIVES TO VIETNAMESE LEARNERS: ADDRESSING PRONUNCIATION CHALLENGES WITH EVIDENCE-BASED METHODS

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Abstract

Pronunciation is a critical component of effective communication in English, directly affecting intelligibility and fluency (Derwing & Munro, 2005). Vietnamese learners often struggle with the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/, which do not exist in their native phonetic inventory, leading to common errors such as pronouncing /θ/ as /s/ or /t/ and /ð/ as /d/ or "z" (Tran & Le, 2022). These mispronunciations can cause misunderstandings, undermining learners' confidence and communicative competence. This study evaluates the effectiveness of three instructional methods—Phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, and Interactive Practice—in teaching these sounds. The practical implications of this research are significant, as it offers insights for educators and researchers specializing in pronunciation teaching and language acquisition. Sixty Vietnamese university students were divided into three groups, with results indicating that Interactive Practice led to the most significant improvement in pronunciation accuracy, followed by Phonetic Training. These findings underscore the importance of combining explicit instruction with interactive practice to enhance pronunciation skills, offering practical guidance for educators.

Keywords: Pronunciation Instruction; Dental Fricatives; Phonetic Training; Interactive Practice; Vietnamese Learners' pronunciation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pronunciation is a critical component of communicative competence and directly influences academic success and overall English language proficiency. From casual conversations to formal academic discourse, pronouncing words accurately is essential for clear communication. Mispronunciation can lead to misunderstandings, hindering effective communication and reducing the speaker's ability to convey their message clearly. (Khamkhien, 2010). In today's globalised world, mastering English pronunciation—particularly challenging sounds like the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/—is crucial for Vietnamese learners aiming to achieve fluency and effective

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communication in English (Cunningham, 2013). Accurate pronunciation enhances both spoken interactions and the speaker's confidence in diverse communicative settings.

Vietnamese learners face special pronunciation issues, particularly in accurately articulating the sounds /θ/ and /ð/, which significantly impact their ability to be comprehended by native English speakers. The difficulty is further intensified by the phonological disparities between Vietnamese, which does not have these sounds, and English (Cunningham, 2013). Empirical research highlights the significant influence of pronunciation on academic achievement, particularly in settings where effective English communication is crucial. Research indicates that a Vietnamese accent in English can impede comprehension of the language's morphosyntax, especially for listeners unfamiliar with it (Dang, 2018). Recent research has shown that learners are becoming more aware of pronunciation's important role in effective communication. It highlights the need for focused instruction that targets specific pronunciation elements challenging for Vietnamese speakers (Vo & Hoang, 2020). Mastering essential pronunciation elements, such as the sounds /θ/ and /ð/, is critical for Vietnamese English learners to communicate effectively and achieve academic success. Customised pronunciation teaching that targets unique phonetic difficulties is essential for these learners to thrive in English-speaking settings.

Although several studies (Ly, 2020; Vo & Hoang, 2020) have examined the difficulties Vietnamese English learners encounter when pronouncing dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/, there is a significant lack of research on effective methods to address these challenges in the Vietnamese educational system. Prior studies (Low, 2021; Thomson & Derwing, 2015) have frequently emphasised the challenges in pronunciation without delving into new research methods or thoroughly examining the educational consequences for this particular group of learners. Most previous research, including the work of Loi (2018), primarily concentrates on identifying troublesome sounds or general pronunciation problems without exploring specific, tailored educational interventions that could be particularly helpful for Vietnamese speakers. Although studies such as Una Cunningham (2013) examine the possibility of teaching and acquiring pronunciation features, they do not provide a specific methodological framework designed to address the distinct phonetic difficulties Vietnamese learners encounter when trying to master the sounds /θ/ and /ð/.

Many studies, including those conducted by Bui (2016), have documented Vietnamese learners' substitution patterns and challenges. However, these studies have not thoroughly explored the specific educational practices that could be implemented to address these difficulties effectively within the Vietnamese educational system. Given these gaps, our research aims to develop and test a specific methodological approach incorporating phonetic training and real-world application exercises tailored for Vietnamese learners. Therefore, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- How effective are different instructional methods—Phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, and Interactive Practice—in improving the pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/ among Vietnamese learners?
- Which instructional method leads to the highest improvement in pronunciation accuracy and learner satisfaction?
- What are the implications of these findings for developing more effective pronunciation teaching strategies within the Vietnamese educational system?

Addressing these questions, the study aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for educators on enhancing the pronunciation skills of Vietnamese learners, ultimately supporting their communicative competence in English-speaking environments.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Phonetic and Phonological Theory

Figure 1 illustrates the impact of phonotactic constraints, phonological rules, feature contrast, perceptual assimilation, and diachronic phonological changes on Vietnamese speakers' perception and production of English sounds. It was adapted from sources such as Cunningham (2013), Pittam and Ingram (1992), Nguyen (2019), and Hansson (2008).

Figure 1 demonstrates the intricate interplay between Vietnamese phonotactic constraints, phonological rules, and Vietnamese speakers' acquisition of English pronunciation. Vietnamese phonotactic constraints significantly influence the perception and production of English sounds, often leading to challenges in English pronunciation. Cunningham (2013) highlights that these constraints, combined with the persistence of Vietnamese phonological rules, result in frequent mispronunciations unless explicitly addressed through targeted teaching interventions.

The concepts of feature contrast and phonological transfer further complicate the acquisition of English pronunciation. As Pittam and Ingram (1992) noted, Vietnamese speakers often struggle with English phonetic features that are absent or markedly different from those in their native language (Pittam & Ingram, 1992). This phonological transfer results from the influence of the first language's phonological system on learning English sounds.

Optimality Theory provides a valuable lens for examining Vietnamese speakers' strategies to approximate English final consonant clusters, which do not exist in Vietnamese. Nguyen (2019) discusses how concepts of phonological markedness and constraints within this theoretical framework can explain the efforts of Vietnamese speakers to overcome native language limitations in their pursuit of accurate English pronunciation (Nguyen, 2019).

Finally, diachronic phonological changes in Vietnamese offer additional insights into contemporary phonetic productions and perceptions. Hansson (2008) emphasises that understanding the historical phonological evolution of Vietnamese can shed light on persistent pronunciation difficulties Vietnamese speakers face when learning English (Hansson, 2008). This comprehensive examination of phonotactic constraints, phonological transfer, and diachronic changes aims to deepen our understanding of the challenges and strategies involved in Vietnamese speakers' acquisition of English pronunciation.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of Phonetic and Phonological Influences on Vietnamese Speakers' English Pronunciation

2.2 Mastering English Phonology and Phonetics for Non-Native Speakers: Applications of SLA Theories

Several Second Language Acquisition (SLA) theories offer practical frameworks for mastering English phonology and phonetics, particularly in addressing pronunciation challenges faced by non-native speakers. These approaches include phonetic training, awareness of phonological processes, and strategies to mitigate language transfer issues.

2.2.1 Speech Learning Model (SLM) and Perceptual Assimilation Model (PAM)

Both the Speech Learning Model (SLM) and the Perceptual Assimilation Model (PAM) suggest that non-native speakers often struggle with sounds absent in their native language (Ying, 2013). Training focused on these sounds can assist learners in developing a more native-like pronunciation (Best et al., 2001). For instance, SLM posits that the ability to learn new sounds declines with age, though this can be mitigated through targeted phonetic training. Furthermore, Mirko Grimaldi et al. (2014) further explore how PAM's principles predict difficulties and the role of targeted training in improving phonetic discrimination and acquisition (Grimaldi et al., 2014). PAM highlights the role of perceptual assimilation, wherein non-native sounds are interpreted through the lens of the learner's native language phonology (Mokari & Werner, 2017). Chunyi Zhou (2018) explores the application of SLM and PAM to second language learners and emphasizes that intensive language exposure and perceptual training help learners develop native-like pronunciation patterns. This process underscores the need for specific training to rewire these perceptual frameworks.

2.2.2 Markedness Differential Hypothesis (MDH)

The MDH posits that features of the target language that are more marked (complex) than those in the learner's first language will be more challenging to acquire (Eckman, 2013). Awareness of these markedness relationships can help educators tailor pronunciation exercises that address these specific challenges (Eckman, 1985). For instance, English phonemes that are

absent or less common in the learner's native language, such as the 'th' sound, may require more intensive practice.

2.2.3 Factors of Age and Exposure

Age and the amount of exposure to the target language significantly affect pronunciation acquisition (Jia et al., 2006; Saito, 2015). Younger learners and those with more immersive exposure tend to achieve better pronunciation. Studies (Kuhl et al., 2003; Tahta et al., 1981) indicate that early exposure to the target language phonology and consistent practice in immersive environments can lead to near-native pronunciation abilities.

2.2.4 Interlanguage Phonology

This approach suggests that learners create an interim phonological system that combines elements from their native language and the target language (Tench, 1996). Understanding this can help in designing interventions that facilitate the transition to more native-like pronunciation patterns (Major, 1998). For example, recognising common patterns in learners' interlanguage phonology can guide the development of specific drills and exercises that target problematic areas.

2.2.5 Use of Technological Tools

Technological resources such as speech analysis software and online pronunciation tutorials can provide learners with immediate feedback and help them practice complex sounds outside the traditional classroom setting, thereby improving their phonetic skills (Bogach et al., 2021; Lambacher, 1999). Tools like spectrograms can visually represent sounds, helping learners understand and correct their pronunciation (Wu & Wu, 2018).

Educators can more effectively address the pronunciation challenges non-native speakers face by integrating these SLA theories into phonological education. These approaches emphasise the importance of targeted phonetic training, awareness of phonological complexity, and the judicious use of technology to enhance learning outcomes.

2.3 Concept of Language Transfer: Vietnamese Influence on English Pronunciation

2.3.1 Negative Transfer

Vietnamese speakers often face difficulties when pronouncing the English sounds /θ/ (as in "think") and /ð/ (as in "this"). A common issue is the substitution of these sounds with phonemes from their first language. For instance, Vietnamese learners frequently replace /θ/ with /t^h/ and /ð/ with /d/ due to the absence of these fricatives in the Vietnamese phonetic inventory and the difficulty of using the tongue and teeth in the new way required for English interdentals (Ly, 2020). Additionally, some learners may mispronounce /ð/ as /z/ and even as /dʒ/, a sound not previously identified as a common substitute, which could further complicate their English pronunciation skill (Bui, 2016). The production of /θ/ and /ð/ requires coordination between the tongue and teeth, which differs significantly from Vietnamese articulatory habits. The difficulty in mastering these new mechanics exacerbates pronunciation errors.

These negative transfer effects underscore the need for targeted instructional interventions that address these specific challenges.

2.3.2 Positive Transfer

While negative transfer dominates the pronunciation challenges for Vietnamese learners, the potential for positive transfer is limited. Vietnamese phonology does not include /θ/ and /ð/

(Pham & McLeod, 2016), leaving learners without analogous sounds to facilitate the acquisition of these English phonemes.

However, the absence of similar fricatives allows learners to focus exclusively on adopting accurate English articulatory patterns without interference from near-similar native sounds. This highlights the importance of explicit instruction and practice in building new phonetic habits.

2.4 Linking Theory to Practice: Pedagogical Approaches in Pronunciation Teaching

2.4.1 Pronunciation Teaching Techniques

Effective teaching of challenging phonemes such as /θ/ and /ð/, which are commonly problematic for Vietnamese learners of English, can be significantly enhanced through a combination of auditory discrimination training, minimal pair drills, and the use of visual aids.

Bui (2016) suggested Auditory Discrimination Training, which involves helping learners develop the ability to distinguish between similar but distinct sounds. For Vietnamese speakers, distinguishing between /θ/ and sounds like [t^h] or [s] is crucial. Auditory discrimination activities can be structured in ways that progressively increase in difficulty, from identifying isolated sounds to discriminating them in varied word positions.

Ly (2020) recommends using minimal pairs (words that differ only by one phoneme, such as "thin" and "tin") as a particularly effective method for improving EFL learners' pronunciation. These drills help differentiate sounds and practice the correct pronunciation in a controlled context. Repeated practice with minimal pairs enhances the learners' phonetic perception and production abilities.

Visual aids, particularly videos and diagrams showing articulatory gestures, are beneficial in pronunciation instruction. Research indicates that learners who observe articulatory gestures, such as tongue placement for /θ/ and /ð/, make significant improvements in production accuracy (Li & Somlak, 2017).

2.4.2 Technology in Language Learning

The role of technology in language learning, especially pronunciation, has grown exponentially with advancements in software and applications designed for language education (Bogach et al., 2021; Demenko et al., 2010; Pennington & Rogerson-Revell, 2019). These technologies offer interactive and user-friendly methods to practice pronunciation outside the traditional classroom setting (Kochem et al., 2022).

Pronunciation Software and Apps could be the best solutions for language learners (Kholis, 2021). Tools such as "ELSA Speak" or "Pronunciation Power" use speech recognition technology to provide immediate feedback on pronunciation (Suragih et al., 2021), which is crucial for mastering difficult phonemes like /θ/ and /ð/. These apps often include features for tracking progress and suggesting targeted exercises based on the learner's performance (Ngo et al., 2023).

Besides, online resources and platforms may offer a range of visual and auditory resources, including instructional videos, pronunciation tutorials, and interactive exercises. These resources allow learners to practice independently and receive instant feedback. Zhang (2003) discusses the use of interactive feedback tools that incorporate visual and auditory elements to improve pronunciation, helping learners compare their articulation with native speakers through visual feedback.

Emerging technologies like VR and AR are beginning to be implemented in pronunciation teaching. AR technology creates immersive learning environments, providing real-world contexts and immediate feedback, which are particularly useful for practicing pronunciation in simulated

scenarios (Azimova & Solidjonov, 2023; Wang & Mughaid, 2022). They simulate real-life interactions where pronunciation is critical in communication, providing a safe space for learners to practice and improve their spoken English.

Linking theoretical insights from language transfer studies to practical teaching methodologies enriches the learning experience and enhances the effectiveness of pronunciation instruction. By incorporating auditory discrimination training, minimal pair drills, visual aids, and leveraging technology, educators can provide comprehensive support to learners struggling with challenging phonemes. This holistic approach addresses the mechanical production of sounds and integrates listening and perceptual skills, which are crucial for real-world language use.

2.5 Challenges faced by Vietnamese English language learners

One of the most intriguing challenges is the tendency for learners to substitute the voiceless /θ/ with /t/ and the voiced /ð/ with /d/. For example, the word "think" is often pronounced as /tɪŋk/ and "this" as /dɪs/ (Slowik & Dung, 2022). This substitution occurs because Vietnamese does not have dental fricatives in its sound inventory, making it difficult for learners to produce these sounds accurately. Slowik and Dung (2022) proposed another issue relating to confusion between the /θ/ and /ð/ sounds, both in listening and pronunciation. Vietnamese speakers may pronounce both "this" and "that" similarly due to the phonetic similarity they perceive between the two sounds. This confusion complicates their ability to distinguish and correctly produce these fricatives in different contexts.

Empirical research (Lee et al., 2015) underscores the impact of pronunciation on academic success. Students need help in environments where clear communication in English is essential. Studies highlight that when not addressed, Vietnamese-accented English can obscure the language's morphosyntax, making comprehension difficult for listeners unfamiliar with the accent (Dang, 2018).

In several cases, learners omit dental fricatives. For example, "month" is pronounced as /mʌn/ (Bui et al., 2021). This phenomenon can be linked to the absence of final fricatives in Vietnamese, which leads learners to drop these sounds entirely at the end of words. Insertion is another standard error, where Vietnamese speakers add an extra vowel sound after the dental fricative, resulting in pronunciations like /tɪŋkə/ for "think" and /dɪsə/ for "this" (Slowik & Dung, 2022). This error is influenced by Vietnamese syllable structure, where syllables typically end in vowels or nasal sounds. The difficulties Vietnamese learners face in pronouncing the /θ/ and /ð/ sounds highlight the need for explicit instruction and targeted practice (Bui, 2016). Addressing these issues through focused teaching methods can help learners overcome these pronunciation challenges and improve their English proficiency.

2.6 Methodological Approaches in Pronunciation Research

Based on examining the efficacy of three instructional methods—Phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, and Interactive Practice—using a quasi-experimental design, several research studies share similar methodological approaches to investigate pronunciation strategies for English dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ among language learners.

The study by Thu Hong and Hong Ha (2022) utilised a quasi-experimental design to assess the effectiveness of video-based shadowing exercises for enhancing EFL learners' pronunciation of English dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. The results indicated significant improvements in

pronunciation accuracy, suggesting that visual and auditory modelling through video can effectively support pronunciation teaching, similar to the study aims' Phonetic Training and Immersive Listening methods (Thu & Hong, 2022).

Another study by Hamzah Haz et al. (2022) implemented a quasi-experimental design to test the effectiveness of the Tongue Twister method in improving students' English pronunciation. This method aligns closely with your Interactive Practice approach, focusing on repetitive articulation and real-time feedback to enhance pronunciation accuracy. The findings demonstrated that tongue twisters were particularly effective in improving pronunciation, similar to the present study's use of role-playing scenarios and peer feedback sessions (Haz et al., 2022).

Jason S. Barrun and Jonald B. Sia's (2023) research also employed a quasi-experimental design to evaluate the effects of teacher-mediated pronunciation instruction on oral language fluency. (Barrun & Sia, 2024). The study involved pre-test and post-test assessments, similar to your methodology, and found significant improvements in the experimental group, underscoring the effectiveness of targeted pronunciation training.

In a flipped classroom, Mohammad Abu El-Magd (2022) investigated the integration of modelling into a flipped classroom approach to developing students' English pronunciation skills at High Institutes for Tourism and Hotels. (Abu El-Magd, 2022). This research also utilised a quasi-experimental design, incorporating both pre-test and post-test evaluations to measure the impact of different instructional strategies on pronunciation accuracy, similar to this study's approach.

Using TikTok-Based Learning, Novitasari (2023) explored TikTok videos for learning English pronunciation through a quasi-experimental design featuring pre-test, mid-test, and post-test assessments. This study focused on interactive and engaging methods to enhance pronunciation skills, aligning with the Interactive Practice method and emphasising learner engagement and satisfaction.

The above-mentioned studies provide valuable references for applying quasi-experimental designs to test various instructional methods for teaching English pronunciation, particularly dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. The methodologies and findings from these studies can provide a robust foundation for comparing and contextualising this research approach.

3. METHODS

This section presents the methodological approach employed to examine the efficacy of three instructional methods—phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, and Interactive Practice—in enhancing the pronunciation of the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ among Vietnamese learners of English. The study investigated the effectiveness of various strategies in improving pronunciation accuracy and Vietnamese learner satisfaction.

3.1 Research Design

The study utilised a quasi-experimental design with three distinct groups to evaluate the effectiveness of instructional methods in improving the pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/ among

Vietnamese learners. This approach aligns with methodologies frequently employed in pronunciation research to assess the comparative impact of different teaching techniques (Álvarez Rojas et al., 2016). Participants were randomly assigned to one of three groups: Phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, or Interactive Practice, ensuring comparability across the experimental conditions. Over eight weeks, each group received 16 hours of targeted instruction, a duration found effective in similar studies to produce measurable improvements in pronunciation (Asmawati & Nurdin, 2023). The research design was explicitly structured to address the primary research question: How effective are these instructional methods in enhancing learners' pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/? Participants' ability to accurately produce /θ/ and /ð/ was assessed before and after the instructional period. The study aimed to generate evidence-based insights into pronunciation teaching strategies by employing this structured approach.

3.2 Participants

Sixty Vietnamese university students ($N=60$) majoring in English language studies were recruited for the study. Participants aged between 18 and 22 had an average of 2.5 years of prior English instruction but no formal training in English pronunciation. This selection criterion aimed to ensure that any improvements in pronunciation could be attributed to the instructional methods tested rather than prior specialised knowledge. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the three groups (20 students per group).

3.3 Instructional Methods

Each group received targeted instruction tailored to different learning strategies to address the research questions regarding the effectiveness of specific instructional methods.

3.3.1 Phonetic Training Group

The Phonetic Training Group received explicit instruction on the articulatory mechanisms required to produce /θ/ and /ð/.

Table: Activities and Tools Used in Phonetic Training

Activity/Tool	Description	Purpose
Articulatory Diagrams	Diagrams showing correct tongue and teeth placement for /θ/ and /ð/.	To visually demonstrate and reinforce correct articulatory positions for producing the sounds.
Phonetic Drills	Minimal pair drills (e.g., "thin" vs. "tin," "this" vs. "dis") were conducted in isolated words and sentences.	To practice and reinforce accurate articulation through repetitive exercises.
Video Demonstrations	Recordings of native speakers pronouncing /θ/ and /ð/ in various contexts.	To provide auditory models for students to imitate and improve pronunciation accuracy.
Auditory Discrimination Exercises	Exercises designed to help students distinguish between /θ/, /ð/ and their	To develop learners' ability to recognise and differentiate

common Vietnamese substitutes between target sounds and similar (/tʰ/, /dʒ/). substitutes.

3.3.2 Immersive Listening Group

The Immersive Listening Group was designed to assess the effectiveness of immersive exposure to natural spoken English in improving the pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/.

Table: Activities and Tools Used in Immersive Listening

Activity/Tool	Description	Purpose
Listening Audiobooks and Podcasts	to Focused on English materials featuring /θ/ and /ð/.	To increase exposure to the natural pronunciation of target sounds in various contexts.
Shadowing Exercises	Participants listened to passages and immediately mimicked native speakers.	To practice accurate pronunciation and improve imitation skills through immediate repetition.
Contextual Listening Practice	She emphasised recognising and mentally marking /θ/ and /ð/ occurrences in dialogues and monologues.	To enhance auditory discrimination and awareness of target sounds in natural speech contexts.

3.3.3 Interactive Practice Group

The Interactive Practice Group was designed to test the hypothesis that structured communicative practice with native speakers and peers would result in the most significant improvement in both pronunciation accuracy and learner satisfaction. This approach involved engaging participants in interactive exercises that provided real-time feedback and practical application of the target sounds /θ/ and /ð/.

Table: Activities and Tools Used in Interactive Practice

Activity/Tool	Description	Purpose
Role-playing Scenarios	Activities involving conversational use of /θ/ and /ð/ (e.g., ordering food, asking for directions).	To practice pronunciation in realistic, everyday contexts and improve conversational fluency.
Peer Feedback Sessions	Students practised dialogues with each other and provided constructive feedback on pronunciation.	To enhance pronunciation accuracy through collaborative learning and peer assessment.
Native Speaker Interaction	Weekly practice sessions with native speakers who provided real-time corrective feedback.	To refine pronunciation skills and gain immediate, expert feedback on target sounds.
Simulation Games	Interactive games that replicated real-life situations to practice and reinforce the correct pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/.	To develop practical pronunciation skills in a fun and engaging manner, reinforcing learning through simulation.

3.4 Procedures

To determine the effectiveness of each instructional method, participants' pronunciation accuracy and satisfaction levels were evaluated pre- and post-intervention.

3.4.1 Pre-test and Post-test

Participants' ability to accurately produce /θ/ and /ð/ was assessed before and after the instructional period.

Table: Assessment Criteria for Evaluating Pronunciation

Criterion	Description	Purpose
Pronunciation Accuracy	Evaluated on a 10-point scale, with 0 indicating no accuracy and 10 indicating native-like pronunciation.	To quantitatively measure the accuracy of participants' pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/.
Audio Recording Analysis	Speech samples were recorded and rated by two phonetic experts and native English speakers on a 1 to 5 scale (1 = poor pronunciation, 5 = native-like pronunciation).	To assess pronunciation clarity and naturalness using expert evaluations.
Inter-rater Reliability	Consistency in evaluations was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85.	To ensure reliable and consistent scoring across different evaluators.

3.4.2 Participant Feedback

To answer the research question regarding learner satisfaction, participants completed a post-intervention questionnaire, rating their satisfaction with the instructional methods and perceived effectiveness on a 5-point Likert scale.

3.5 Research Instrument

3.5.1 Pre-Test and Post-Test

The pre-and post-tests were integral components of the study's instrument, designed to measure the effectiveness of the instructional methods on pronunciation accuracy of the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. Both tests included a series of tasks: isolated word pronunciation, sentence context pronunciation, and minimal pair discrimination. Participants were assessed before and after the intervention, with scores ranging from 0 (no accuracy) to 10 (native-like pronunciation). The comparison of pre-and post-test scores allowed for an evaluation of improvement in pronunciation skills, providing objective data on the effectiveness of each instructional method used in the study.

3.5.2 Post-Intervention Questionnaire

A post-intervention questionnaire was administered to evaluate learner satisfaction, and the perceived effectiveness of the instructional methods used in the study. The questionnaire aimed to gather participants' subjective feedback on their experiences with the three instructional methods: Phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, and Interactive Practice. It consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of learners' attitudes and perceptions.

The closed-ended questions used a 5-point Likert scale to measure various aspects of learner satisfaction, including overall satisfaction with the instructional method, engagement levels, perceived effectiveness in improving pronunciation of the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/, and confidence gained from the training. Specific questions also focused on the usefulness of the activities (such as role-playing, phonetic drills, and shadowing exercises) and the helpfulness of feedback provided during the sessions.

In addition to the quantitative items, the questionnaire included open-ended questions that invited participants to share their thoughts on what they found most helpful, what aspects could be improved, and any additional suggestions for enhancing pronunciation instruction. This combination of quantitative and qualitative data provided a holistic understanding of the learners' experiences and insights into each instructional method's strengths and potential areas for improvement.

The results from this post-intervention questionnaire addressed the second research question concerning which instructional method led to the highest levels of learner satisfaction and perceived effectiveness. The feedback helped identify the most effective strategies for teaching pronunciation to Vietnamese learners of English, contributing to evidence-based recommendations for pronunciation instruction.

3.6 Bias Mitigation Strategies

Several bias mitigation strategies were implemented throughout the study to enhance the validity of the findings and ensure the research questions were effectively addressed.

Firstly, **random assignment** was utilised to prevent selection bias by ensuring an equal distribution of participants across the three instructional groups (Kahan et al., 2015). This approach helped to balance any pre-existing differences among participants, providing a more accurate comparison of the instructional methods' effectiveness.

Secondly, **assessors were blinded to the group assignments to avoid assessment bias. The assessors who evaluated the participants' pronunciation accuracy were blinded to the group assignments. This strategy ensured that the evaluations were unbiased and based solely on the quality of the pronunciation** rather than any preconceived expectations related to the instructional group.

In addition, **standardised instructions** were used to maintain consistency across different groups and instructors. A standardised curriculum was followed for all instructional sessions, ensuring that each group received uniform guidance and content, thereby reducing any variability in instruction that could affect the study's outcomes.

Lastly, the study included a strategy to control external variables by assessing participants' prior exposure to English media during recruitment. This assessment helped to account for any external influences that could have impacted the participants' pronunciation skills outside the instructional sessions.

This rigorous methodological framework is designed to provide comprehensive insights into the most effective instructional strategies for teaching the pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/ to Vietnamese learners of English, directly addressing the research questions posed.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Effectiveness of Instructional Methods in Improving Pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/

Pre-test and Post-test Assessments

The effectiveness of the instructional methods was evaluated through pre-test and post-test assessments. The tests measured the accuracy of pronouncing θ and ð, with scores ranging from 0 to 10, where 0 indicates no accuracy, and 10 indicates perfect accuracy. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Pre-test and Post-test Scores

Group	Pre-test Score	Mean	Post-test Score	Mean Improvement
Phonetic Training Group	3.2		7.8	4.6
Immersive Listening Group	3.5		6.5	3.0
Interactive Practice Group	3.0		8.0	5.0

Phonetic Training Group: Participants showed significant improvement, with mean scores increasing from 3.2 to 7.8, resulting in a mean improvement of 4.6 points. This improvement suggests that explicit phonetic training, which emphasises articulatory mechanisms, effectively enhances pronunciation accuracy.

Immersive Listening Group: This group also demonstrated improvement, with mean scores rising from 3.5 to 6.5, indicating a mean improvement of 3.0 points. While immersive listening was beneficial for increasing phonetic awareness, the improvement was less pronounced than other methods, suggesting it may not be as effective for achieving precise articulation.

Interactive Practice Group: The Interactive Practice Group exhibited the highest improvement, with scores increasing from 3.0 to 8.0, yielding a mean improvement of 5.0 points. These findings highlight the effectiveness of interactive, real-time feedback and practice with native speakers in improving pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/.

Audio Recordings

The effectiveness of the instructional methods was further evaluated by analysing audio recordings of participants' speech using Praat software. The software provided detailed measurements of various phonetic parameters, including formant frequencies, pitch, intensity, and frication noise patterns, to assess the pronunciation accuracy of /θ/ and /ð/ sounds. The results are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Pronunciation Analysis Results Using Praat Software

Group	Pre-test Mean Formant Deviation (Hz)	Post-test Mean Formant Deviation (Hz)	Mean Improvement (Hz)
Phonetic Training Group	200	50	150
Immersive Listening Group	250	100	150
Interactive Practice Group	300	30	270

Phonetic Training Group showed a significant reduction in formant deviation from the native-like standard, with pre-test deviations averaging 200 Hz and post-test deviations averaging 50 Hz. This improvement of 150 Hz indicates substantial progress in achieving native-like pronunciation, likely due to focused articulatory training.

The Immersive Listening Group also demonstrated improvement, with mean formant deviation decreasing from 250 Hz in the pre-test to 100 Hz in the post-test. Although the improvement (150 Hz) was notable, it was less pronounced than in the Interactive Practice Group, suggesting that while immersive exposure aids in phonetic awareness, it may not be as effective for achieving precise articulation.

Participants in the Interactive Practice Group exhibited the most significant improvement, with mean formant deviation decreasing from 300 Hz to 30 Hz and improving to 270 Hz. This substantial enhancement in pronunciation accuracy highlights the effectiveness of interactive, real-time feedback and practice in achieving near-native pronunciation.

In addition to formant analysis, Praat software provided results insights into other acoustic features, such as pitch variation and intensity modulation. Regarding the pitch variation, the Interactive Practice Group aligned most significantly with native speaker pitch patterns, indicating improved intonation and stress application. According to the results of the intensity modulation, the Phonetic Training Group achieved greater consistency in intensity levels, suggesting enhanced control over speech loudness and emphasis.

Interactive Practice resulted in the most significant improvement in formant accuracy (270 Hz), followed by Phonetic Training and Immersive Listening (150 Hz each). These results corroborate the pre-test and post-test findings, emphasising that active feedback and application foster better phonetic acquisition.

4.2 Instructional Method Leading to the Highest Improvement and Learner Satisfaction

Participants provided subjective feedback via a questionnaire designed to measure their satisfaction and perceived effectiveness of the instructional methods, using a 5-point scale (1 = "very dissatisfied/ineffective," 5 = "very satisfied/effective"). The results, summarised in Table 3, highlight differences in **satisfaction and perceived effectiveness across three instructional**

groups: the Phonetic Training Group, the Immersive Listening Group, and the Interactive Practice Group.

Table 3: Participant Feedback

Group	Satisfaction Rating	Perceived Effectiveness
Phonetic Training Group	4.2	4.5
Immersive Listening Group	3.8	4.0
Interactive Practice Group	4.5	4.8

The Phonetic Training Group demonstrated high satisfaction levels, with a mean score of 4.2 and a perceived effectiveness score of 4.5. These ratings suggest that participants valued the explicit instruction provided through phonetic training and perceived it as beneficial and satisfactory.

Although the Immersive Listening Group reported generally positive feedback, it showed slightly lower satisfaction (3.8) and perceived effectiveness (4.0) than the other groups. While the participants appreciated immersive listening, the results indicate that it may not have resonated as strongly as other instructional approaches.

The Interactive Practice Group had the highest ratings, with satisfaction rated at 4.5 and perceived effectiveness at 4.8. These results highlight a clear preference for interactive learning methods, suggesting that participants found this approach highly engaging and effective in supporting their learning outcomes.

Overall, the data reflects the participants' inclination towards interactive and explicit methods of instruction, with a comparatively moderate reception of immersive listening techniques.

4.3 Implications for Pronunciation Teaching Strategies

Blended Instructional Approach

The findings suggest that a blended instructional approach, combining explicit phonetic training with interactive practice, is the most effective strategy for teaching Vietnamese learners to pronounce /θ/ and /ð/. Explicit phonetic training is supported by the Speech Learning Model (SLM), which highlights the importance of targeted instruction in helping learners develop new articulatory habits for non-native sounds (Best et al., 2001). This is particularly relevant for Vietnamese learners, who often substitute /θ/ and /ð/ with /t/ or /d/ due to the absence of these fricatives in their native phonology (Ly, 2020). Through guided drills and visual aids, explicit training helps learners internalise correct tongue placement and airflow control, laying the foundation for accurate pronunciation.

However, interactive practice is indispensable to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical application. Celce-Murcia et al. (2010) emphasise incorporating communicative activities, such as role-playing and peer feedback, to contextualise phonetic knowledge and enhance fluency. This study's findings align with their work, as participants in the Interactive Practice group demonstrated the highest gains in pronunciation accuracy and satisfaction. Additionally, immersive listening is a valuable supplementary tool, enhancing learners' exposure

to native-like pronunciation patterns. Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985) underscores the role of comprehensible input in language acquisition, and listening to audiobooks or podcasts featuring /θ/ and /ð/ reinforces learners' ability to recognise these sounds in natural contexts. As Foote et al. (2016) suggested, pairing immersive listening with shadowing exercises further bridges the gap between perception and production.

Use of Technology

Integrating technology into pronunciation instruction offers significant opportunities to enhance learner outcomes and teaching efficiency. Speech analysis tools, such as Praat and pronunciation apps like ELSA Speak, provide learners with immediate, data-driven feedback on their articulation accuracy. These tools allow learners to visualise critical features of their speech, such as formant frequencies and intensity modulation, facilitating self-correction and promoting autonomy (Fabre-Merchán et al., 2017). For instance, Praat was used in this study to measure improvements in formant accuracy, with the Interactive Practice group demonstrating the most substantial gains. Incorporating such tools into classroom instruction can replicate these benefits at scale.

Interactive platforms further support learner engagement by enabling dynamic, real-world practice. Virtual simulations and gamified activities create low-pressure environments for learners to practice /θ/ and /ð/, increasing their confidence and reducing anxiety. For example, Novitasari (2023) demonstrated the potential of TikTok-based learning for improving English pronunciation through short, interactive videos. By incorporating similar tools, educators can provide learners with diverse, engaging methods to reinforce their skills both inside and outside the classroom.

Customizing Pedagogy

Tailoring pronunciation instruction to address the specific challenges faced by Vietnamese learners is critical. Negative transfer from the learners' first language often results in the substitution of /θ/ with /t/ and /ð/ with /d/, as documented by Bui et al. (2021). These persistent errors require targeted interventions, such as minimal pair drills (e.g., "thin" vs. "tin" or "this" vs. "dis"), which explicitly contrast the problematic sounds with their substitutes. Studies like Ly (2020) emphasise the importance of diagnostic assessments to identify learners' unique difficulties, enabling educators to design exercises that directly address these errors.

Cultural and linguistic differences must also be considered when customising pedagogy. Vietnamese syllable structures and tonal features often interfere with learners' ability to produce English sounds, particularly in stress and intonation accurately (Dang, 2018). Multisensory teaching methods, such as using physical gestures to demonstrate tongue placement or videos showing articulatory movements, can make abstract phonetic concepts more accessible to learners. Moreover, leveraging peer feedback and native-speaker interactions, as suggested by Vygotsky's sociocultural theory (1978), promotes collaborative learning and accelerates phonetic acquisition in social contexts.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Effectiveness of Instructional Methods in Improving Pronunciation

This study demonstrated that all three instructional methods—Phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, and Interactive Practice—positively influenced the pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/ among Vietnamese learners, albeit to varying degrees.

Phonetic Training, which emphasised explicit instruction on articulatory mechanisms, resulted in substantial gains in pronunciation accuracy, with an average improvement of 4.6 points in post-test scores. This outcome aligns with the Speech Learning Model (SLM), which emphasises the importance of detailed phonetic instruction for acquiring non-native sounds (Best et al., 2001). Participants benefited from focused practice using articulatory diagrams, minimal pair drills, and auditory discrimination exercises, which helped them internalise the physical mechanics of producing /θ/ and /ð/.

Immersive Listening also led to improvement, albeit less pronounced, with an average gain of 3.0 points. While this method enhanced learners' exposure to native-like pronunciation patterns, it proved less effective in fostering precise articulation. This finding aligns with Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985), which posits that exposure to comprehensible input aids language acquisition but may not sufficiently address production difficulties without active engagement (Foote et al., 2016).

The Interactive Practice method exhibited the highest improvement, with participants achieving an average gain of 5.0 points in pronunciation accuracy. Role-playing scenarios, peer feedback sessions, and interaction with native speakers created an environment that encouraged learners to apply phonetic skills in meaningful, communicative contexts. These results align with Celce-Murcia et al. (2010), who emphasize the effectiveness of blending explicit instruction with communicative practice in fostering phonological development.

5.2 Instructional Method Leading to the Highest Improvement and Learner Satisfaction

Among the three methods, Interactive Practice emerged as the most effective in enhancing both pronunciation accuracy and learner satisfaction. The combination of real-time feedback, dynamic interaction, and contextualized practice addressed learners' needs for both accurate articulation and practical application of /θ/ and /ð/ in communication. Participants in this group not only demonstrated the greatest improvements in pronunciation scores but also reported the highest levels of satisfaction (4.5) and perceived effectiveness (4.8). These findings underscore the importance of interactive and engaging teaching methods in fostering learner motivation and phonetic acquisition.

In contrast, Phonetic Training was highly effective in building learners' foundational understanding of articulation, as reflected in their substantial gains in accuracy. Participants appreciated the explicit instruction, giving it a high perceived effectiveness score (4.5). However,

some learners noted a lack of practical application, suggesting that the method might benefit from integration with communicative activities.

While Immersive Listening is valuable for enhancing exposure, it received lower ratings for satisfaction (3.8) and perceived effectiveness (4.0). Feedback from participants highlighted its limitations in facilitating active learning. Many learners preferred methods that provided more opportunities for hands-on practice and immediate feedback.

These findings suggest that while all three methods have merits, combining their strengths may lead to more comprehensive instructional strategies that balance foundational learning with real-world application.

5.3 Implications for Developing Pronunciation Teaching Strategies

The study's findings provide actionable insights for designing pronunciation teaching strategies tailored to Vietnamese learners. First, the success of Interactive Practice highlights the importance of incorporating contextualized and communicative activities into instruction. Language instructors should prioritize methods that offer opportunities for real-world application, such as role-playing, peer collaboration, and native speaker interaction. These activities not only improve accuracy but also enhance learner confidence and engagement.

Second, Phonetic Training should remain a cornerstone of pronunciation instruction, particularly for addressing sounds absent in learners' native phonology. Explicit instruction using visual aids, drills, and diagnostic tools ensures learners develop a solid understanding of articulatory mechanisms. However, as seen in this study, this approach is most effective when complemented by interactive methods that facilitate practical application.

Finally, Immersive Listening, while less impactful on its own, remains a valuable supplementary tool for increasing learners' auditory exposure to native-like pronunciation patterns. When paired with shadowing exercises, it bridges the gap between perception and production, reinforcing learners' ability to recognize and replicate challenging sounds.

By blending these methods, educators can create a holistic instructional framework that addresses the unique challenges faced by Vietnamese learners. The integration of technological tools, such as speech analysis software and interactive platforms, can further enhance teaching effectiveness and learner outcomes. Future research should explore the long-term effects of such blended strategies and investigate their applicability to other learner demographics and phonetic challenges.

6. CONCLUSION

This study explored the effectiveness of three instructional methods—phonetic Training, Immersive Listening, and Interactive Practice—in teaching Vietnamese learners how to pronounce the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. The findings demonstrate that while all methods led to

improvements, a combination of explicit phonetic training and interactive practice produced the most significant results regarding pronunciation accuracy and learner satisfaction.

The Phonetic Training group showed substantial gains in understanding the articulatory mechanisms of these challenging sounds, improving pronunciation accuracy and learner confidence. However, the Interactive Practice group exhibited the highest overall improvement, underscoring the importance of real-world application and feedback in pronunciation training. While beneficial for enhancing phonetic awareness, immersion listening proved less effective in isolation.

These results provide valuable insights for educators aiming to enhance pronunciation instruction. Combining explicit phonetic instruction with opportunities for interactive practice is critical for addressing the unique pronunciation challenges faced by Vietnamese learners of English. Future research should explore how these methods can be integrated into a comprehensive language-learning curriculum, possibly expanding the study to include different learner demographics or language pairs.

By adopting these instructional strategies, educators can foster greater communicative competence and confidence in their learners, ultimately improving their ability to function in English-speaking environments

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Pre-test and Post-test Assessments

A.1 Pre-test Assessment

The pre-test assessment aimed to evaluate the baseline pronunciation accuracy of /θ/ and /ð/ among Vietnamese learners before the instructional interventions. The assessment included three components: isolated word pronunciation, sentence context pronunciation, and minimal pair discrimination.

1. Isolated Word Pronunciation Test

Objective: To assess the ability to accurately produce /θ/ and /ð/ sounds in isolation.

Procedure: Participants were asked to pronounce a list of words containing the target sounds.

Word List:

θ/ Words	/ð/ Words
thin	this
think	that
bath	bathe
thumb	feather
path	breathe
theory	these
cloth	mother
thousand	together
both	rather
healthy	brother

Scoring: Each word was scored on a 10-point scale (0 = no accuracy, 10 = native-like pronunciation).

2. Sentence Context Pronunciation Test

Objective: To evaluate the ability to pronounce /θ/ and /ð/ within sentences.

Procedure: Participants were asked to read sentences that included the target sounds.

Sentence List

/θ/ Sentences	/ð/ Sentences
"I think he went to the north."	"This is the brother of that man."
"The path to the theater is narrow."	"They breathe the fresh air every day."
"The thief hid beneath the thick bush."	"She loves her mother more than anything."

"They threw the ball through the window."	"These clothes are theirs, not ours."
"The third Thursday of this month is a holiday."	"I'd rather go with them than stay here."

Scoring: Each sentence was scored on a 10-point scale based on the accuracy of /θ/ and /ð/ production.

3. Minimal Pair Discrimination Test

Objective: To test the learner's ability to distinguish between minimal pairs involving /θ/ and /ð/.

Procedure: Participants were presented with a list of minimal pairs and asked to pronounce each pair.

Minimal Pairs List:

- thin - sin
- that - bat
- thought - taught
- they - day
- thigh - tie
- this - hiss
- there - dare
- three - tree
- though - dough
- with - wit

Scoring: Each pair was scored on a binary scale (correct/incorrect) for discrimination accuracy.

A.2 Post-test Assessment

The post-test assessment followed the same structure as the pre-test to measure improvements in pronunciation accuracy following the instructional interventions.

1. Isolated Word Pronunciation Test

Procedure: Participants repeated the pronunciation of the same word list used in the pre-test.

Scoring: Each word was scored on a 10-point scale (0 = no accuracy, 10 = native-like pronunciation).

2. Sentence Context Pronunciation Test

Procedure: Participants read the same sentences from the pre-test to ensure comparability.

Scoring: Each sentence was scored on a 10-point scale based on the accuracy of /θ/ and /ð/ production.

3. Minimal Pair Discrimination Test

Procedure: Participants were asked to pronounce the same minimal pairs as in the pre-test.

Scoring: Each pair was scored on a binary scale (correct/incorrect).

A.3 Scoring and Analysis

- **Pronunciation Accuracy:** Assessed using the 10-point scale for words and sentences.
- **Audio Recording Analysis:** Speech samples were recorded and rated by two phonetic experts and native English speakers on a 1 to 5 scale (1 = poor pronunciation, 5 = native-like pronunciation).
- **Inter-rater Reliability:** Consistency in evaluations was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85, ensuring reliable scoring across different evaluators

Appendix 2: Post-Intervention Questionnaire: Learner Satisfaction and Perceived Effectiveness

Instructions: This questionnaire aims to gather your feedback on the instructional method you experienced in this study. Your responses are valuable in understanding the effectiveness of the method and improving future pronunciation teaching strategies. Please answer all questions honestly based on your experience.

Section 1: General Satisfaction

1. **Overall, how satisfied are you with the instructional method used in this study?**
 - Very Dissatisfied (1)
 - Dissatisfied (2)
 - Neutral (3)
 - Satisfied (4)
 - Very Satisfied (5)
2. **How engaging did you find the lessons?**
 - Not Engaging at All (1)
 - Slightly Engaging (2)
 - Neutral (3)
 - Engaging (4)
 - Very Engaging (5)
3. **How well did the instructional method help you understand the pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/?**
 - Not at All (1)
 - Slightly (2)
 - Moderately (3)
 - Well (4)
 - Very Well (5)

Section 2: Perceived Effectiveness

4. **How effective was the instructional method in improving your pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/?**
 - Not Effective at All (1)
 - Slightly Effective (2)
 - Moderately Effective (3)
 - Effective (4)
 - Very Effective (5)
5. **Do you feel more confident in pronouncing /θ/ and /ð/ after this training?**
 - Not at All Confident (1)
 - Slightly Confident (2)
 - Neutral (3)
 - Confident (4)
 - Very Confident (5)
6. **How likely are you to use the techniques learned in this study to continue improving your pronunciation?**
 - Very Unlikely (1)
 - Unlikely (2)
 - Neutral (3)
 - Likely (4)
 - Very Likely (5)

Section 3: Specific Aspects of the Instructional Method

7. **How effective were the specific activities to improve (e.g., role-playing, phonetic drills, shadowing exercises) in helping you learn the correct pronunciation of /θ/ and /ð/?**
 - Not Effective at All (1)
 - Slightly Effective (2)
 - Moderately Effective (3)
 - Effective (4)
 - Very Effective (5)
8. **How helpful was the feedback provided during the sessions?**
 - Not Helpful at All (1)
 - Slightly Helpful (2)
 - Neutral (3)
 - Helpful (4)
 - Very Helpful (5)
9. **Did the instructional method address your specific pronunciation challenges with /θ/ and /ð/?**
 - Not at All (1)
 - Slightly (2)
 - Neutral (3)
 - Well (4)
 - Very Well (5)

Section 4: Open-Ended Questions

10. **What did you find most helpful about the instructional method?**
(Open-ended response)
11. **What aspects of the instructional method could be improved?**
(Open-ended response)
12. **Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for improving pronunciation instruction?**
(Open-ended response)

Thank you for taking the time to provide your feedback. Your responses will help us improve the effectiveness of pronunciation teaching methods for future learners.